

Workers' Participation in Decision Making and Performance of Public Sector Organization in Enugu State Local Governments, Nigeria

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Abstract

The impact of decision-making on organizational performance cannot be overemphasized. There is a common believe among management theorists that decision-making is one of the most important of all management activities. It is also generally believed that workers' participation in decision making has positive impact on the overall performance of any organization. Therefore, this work is an assessment of workers' participation in decision making and its impact on public sector performance with particular reference to Enugu state local government system. The researcher adopted the use of both primary and secondary data. The study adopts a descriptive method of research. The population size of the study is five hundred and ninety-five (595) junior and senior staff drawn from the seventeen (17) local governments in Enugu state. Thirty-five (35) staff from each local government sample size is three hundred and forty staff determined by Taro Yamani's statistical formula. The sample size comprises of 137 junior staff of 17 local governments and 102 senior staff. Each local government comprises of 8 junior and 6 senior staff. Therefore, fourteen (14) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to each local government which amounted to a total number of 239 copies of the questionnaire to get information on the major areas of concern. The data collected for this study was analyzed using tables, percentages and averages. The hypothesis was calculated with the use of chi-square (X^2). The study adopted McGregor's theory x and y as a framework of analysis. Several findings which include the strategies through which the skills and abilities of workers could be maximized in any organization will be unveiled. The study made some recommendations which include that further research on the subject matter should be conducted.

Keywords: Decision, Making, Workers, Participation, Staff, government

Introduction

The impact of decision making on the performance of any organization cannot be over-emphasized. Decision making is a key management function. There is a common notion among management theorists that decision is one of the most important of all management activities. Administrators of organization must among other things, make decisions concerning human resources management. Therefore, decision making is an ever-present phenomenon in organizations, so important that management cannot take place without decisions, as organizations must (through the workers), think and decide on issues confronting them.

Decision making can be said to be a complete chain of events through which any organization makes and implements decisions. Workers' participation in decision has implication on the performance of any organization. It can as well be referred to as a deliberate selection in a given alternatives or a means of actualizing a pre-determined goals in any organization, (Iranwanto, 2015). A considerable number of researches that has been carried out posit that "Developing countries such as Nigeria can achieve maximum degree of development if the development process acknowledges people's participation". If the dividend of development plans in any organization is for the well-being of the common man, it is necessary that every stage of the process encompasses the full participation of its workers. According to V. Subramanian in Nwizu (2002), "The outcome of any programme of action hinges on the responses which it receives from the people and the class of people the programme intends to benefit.

The style of leadership impacts heavily on the decision-making process of any organization. Democratic style of leadership encourages group involvement in decision making hence, orders are given only after consultations and explanations. The workers are encouraged to exhibit initiatives and creativity. On the contrary, autocratic style of leadership is highly rigid and dogmatic, has a strong belief about how certain procedures should be carried out, hence, not willing to consider new ideas or initiatives. In view of the changing nature of organizations and environment, democratic leaders are more likely to be productive and efficient organizational members. Consequent upon the impact of decision making on organizational performance, it is worthy of note that managers, alone should not make decisions, rather, employees at every level in any organization should participate in decision making. One style of democratic leadership which has recently received good attention is known as employee participation. Generally, a programme of participation is an attempt to involve subordinates in the operation of the business. Encouraging subordinates to take part in some part of the supervisors' decision making enhances performance, an act which ordinarily would not be tolerated in many organizations, (Katz and Kahn, 1979). Participation creates room for workers to become identified with the organization thus, makes work more meaningful. On the contrary, in any organization whereby every important decision is restricted to the supervisor, participation management places the subordinate on entirely different footing. Accordingly, the essence of decision making is to direct human actions towards a future goal, choosing among alternative course of actions. If there were no alternatives, there

would be no need for decision. To this end, the most important activities of management are decision making. The need to decide remains the preoccupation of management in any type of organization both through voluntary and non-voluntary organizations. Most of the times, managers perceive decision making as their core job as they must, at one time or the other choose what should be done, who, where and how it should be done.

Traditionally, management are known to assert much influence over the ordinary workers particularly, their immediate subordinate. Thus, in many occasions, superiors make unilateral decisions, even in areas which directly affect their subordinates. The impact of participation on one's sense of accomplishment is substantial. Engaging the individuals mind as well as his hands in the operation of the organization makes him mere integral part of the organization. To this regard, his contribution becomes more significance, thus, he realizes that he is more than a human machine.

Participation positively impacts not only on the workers but, extends to the management as management taps the thinking of workers and benefits from workers contributions and their enthusiastic work (Lundgrem, 1982). The benefits of workers participation in decision making also includes more knowledge and expertise available to solve problems, hence, greater number of alternatives are examined, the final decision is better understood and accepted by all, and there is more commitment among all to make the final decision to work. There is no doubt that these will go a long way to facilitate individual, group and organizational effectiveness as two good heads are better than one.

Against this background, the thrust of this work is to assess the participation of workers in decision making and its implication on the performance of public sector organization with particular reference to Enugu state local government system.

Study Area/Methodology

The study was carried out in Enugu state of Nigeria. The state is loosely regarded as Wawa or Coal City state with area code 042. It was created on the 27th day of August 1991 from the then old Anambra state, with its capital presently Enugu, ranked 22 out of 36 states based on 2006 population census with a total population of about 3,267,837. Enugu state comprises of Enugu, Udi, Nsukka and Orji River as the major cities respectively. It has a common boundary with Abia state and Imo state to the southern part, Ebonyi state to the East, Benue state to the northeast, Kogi state to the northwest and Anambra state to the west. Based

on the figures generated from the 2006 population census, Enugu state has a population of about 3,267,837 people and the estimate of about 3.8 million in 2012. The state is a conglomeration of the Igbos in the southeast which is the majority and Idoma/Igala people in Ette (Igbo-eze North) of Enugu State which is the minority (Wikipedia, 2017).

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The population used for this study is 12,011 junior and senior staff of the seventeen 17 local governments in Enugu state. This was collected through simple random sampling techniques. According to the office of the Head of Service Enugu state Secretariat, 2016, Nsukka has a total number of 1,025, Uzo-uwani 1,001, Igbo-Etiti 1, 010, Aninri 600, Awgu 520, Enugu East 815, Enugu North 706, Enugu South 620, Ezeagu 600, Igbo-Eze North 604, Igbo-Eze South 520, Isi-Uzo 505, Nkanu East 620 Nkanu West 715, Orji River 700, Udenu 710, Udi 740. These amounts to total number of 8009 junior and 4002 senior staff in the 17 Local Government Area of Enugu State. To reduce the data collected into meaningful form, data were presented and analyzed in statistical tables and charts (pie charts, bar charts, histograms and frequency polygon). The analytical induction of data was done thematically by explaining, transcribing and describing conceptual issues used to examine existence of association among variables.

Literature Review

Workers Participation in Decision Making and Organizational Performance

Miller & Monge (1986), opines that, organizations that offer employees with more autonomy have more committed and productive workforce and consequently, a reduced turnover rate. One of the reasons why an employee will embark on something like study leave and decided not to come back again to the organization is simply because his ideas would not be utilized once he completes the programme. It is the culture of the public service to be bureaucratic due to the sensitive nature of the job. It is also worthy to acknowledge the fact that decisions made within the public service can affect not only the workers, but the country as a whole. According to Miller & Prichard, workers who are interested in participation are usually younger, more interested in career advancement, more optimistic about programme advantages and more active in their union than the uninterested ones.

The link between participation and performance ranges from both the individual level and organizational level. Participation in decision making makes it possible to adopt and apply the best alternative in performing a proposed action. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the best possible way among different ways of performing a task hence; the one finally chosen should be capable of producing the best result which can be accepted to both the workers and management to the satisfaction of all. A satisfied workforce puts in their best efforts which in turn results to increased output to the satisfaction of management who may come forward to share the gain with the workers. This leads to improvement in the overall performance of the organization. Bell, C. & Mjoli, T., (2014), states that, decision is the essence of management.

. According to Spreitzer et al., (1997), workers that have greater choice concerning how to perform their duties have been discovered to have a high job satisfaction and high performance.

Government policy promotes workers participation as a tool to enhance organizational performance. Participatory measures such as team working and high involvement work practices demonstrates improvement in performance, but can also have less positive outcomes for workers and social wellbeing. Performance changes may occur because participation leads to changed attitudes and consequently, higher performance.

Workers' participation in decision making when viewed from the point of improving performance and workplace conditions, requires the individual work's direct participation in the decision making or the organization (Summers, J., & Hyman, J., (2005). Generally, the workers have more knowledge and information about the work process than the managers, and are better placed to achieve improved performance. Workers' participation provides them with greater internal rewards than the authoritarian style of management. These rewards are capable of increasing satisfaction and motivate them to achieve goals. By granting employees greater access to management information, mutual trust and commitment will be actualized. It is worthy to note that improve performance can be ascertained against such yardsticks as, increased productivity, efficiency, profitability and increased workers commitment, operational flexibility, product quality and actualization of targets.

Gap in literature

In view of the literatures cited, the effects of the external economic, political and social environment on participatory measures were not acknowledged. Lack of consistency in the

results of participatory processes suggests that participatory schemes cannot be discussed in isolation from the economic, political and social environments. The impacts of participation schemes vary with the environment into which they are introduced. An insecure environment may compel workers to adhere to participatory measures, yet the required or expected commitment may not be achieved.

Another gap discovered in the literature is the corresponding assumption that if an employer gives his employees more autonomy in the day to day running of the business or more decision-making opportunity through participation, it can strengthen their commitment and performance even though the relationship and incentives are not there. Participation cannot single handedly increase performance or achieve desired result. The potential for positive effect of participation on performance seems to arise when participatory measures are used in combination with other welfare measures; there is the tendency of enhancing organizational performance. Changes in employees' attitudes and behaviour can be achieved through financial participation, by allowing the employees to have a stake in the organization. Also, by taking care of workers social needs through improved job security and satisfaction as well as improvement in the quality of working life, performance will be increased. Workers are not homogenous group that can have uniform responses to participation schemes, strategies or initiatives. Some respond to financial incentives while others to a more social or work-related motivations. Therefore, a combination of financial or monetary and non-monetary or work – related participation appears to strike a balance as regards performance.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The proper understanding of the correlation between workers participation in decision making and performance of public sector organization, can be achieved through McGregor's Theory X and Y. Theory X and Theory Y was an idea devised by Douglas McGregor in his book *The Human Side of Enterprise* 1960. According to Lerner, (2011), "what he sought in general, and perhaps more profoundly, was a better understanding of how human factors affected, and were incorporated into, organizational behavior and outcomes". Douglas McGregor's Theory X assumes that human beings are lazy, hence, do not want to work. Therefore, it is the job of the manager to force or coerce them to work. McGregor's Theory X makes these basic assumptions thus:

- ❖ The average man dislikes work and can do anything to deviate from it.

- ❖ Most people need to be coerced, controlled, directed, and threatened to put them in line towards organizational goals.
- ❖ The average man prefers to be directed to avoid responsibility, has relatively little ambition, and puts job security above his ambition.
- ❖ Is self-centered and therefore does not care about organizational goals.
- ❖ Resists change.
- ❖ Is gullible and not particularly intelligent.

According to this theory, responsibility for showing initiative and motivation lies with the employee hence; he takes the blame for any act of failure to perform. Workers are motivated by external benefits such as monetary rewards, promotion and tenure rather than participatory decision making, (Helms, 2006). The implication of theory X is that if organizational goals are to be met, there is need for the manager to structure the work and mobilize workers. To this regard, the manager needs to adopt the authoritarian leadership style whereby the decision making power lies with manager.

On the contrary, theory Y posits that workers would behave differently if treated differently by managers. Theory Y is on the assumption that the higher order needs super cedes the lower hence, dominates individuals. Theory Y is based on six (6) assumptions as follows:

- ❖ The average man sees work as a vital component of his existence hence, do not hate work.
- ❖ Individuals exercise self-direction and control so as to achieve objectives.
- ❖ Self-efforts demonstrated to achieve organizational goals amounts to rewards of self-satisfaction and self-actualization.
- ❖ The average man accepts as well as seeks responsibility.
- ❖ Man is creative and imaginative when it comes to solving organizational problems.
- ❖ The intellectual potential of the average man is only partially realized.

Under these assumptions, there is an opportunity to align personal goals with organizational goals by using the employee's own quest for fulfillment as the motivator. McGregor stressed that Theory Y management does not imply a soft approach.

McGregor recognized that some people may not have reached the level of maturity assumed by Theory Y and therefore may need tighter controls that can be relaxed as the employee develops. Theory X and Y created by McGregor has been a valid basic principle from which

to develop positive management style and techniques. McGregor's ideas suggest that there are two fundamental approaches to managing people. Several managers influenced by theory x, and generally get poor results. On the other hand, liberal managers use theory y, which produces better performance and results, and allows people to grow and develop.

The utility of this theory on Enugu State Local Governments is the need to tap the inherent potentials of workers as unveiled by McGregor's theory "Y" through participation in decision making to boost performance and actualize the organizational goals. McGregor opines that theory "Y" managers are more likely to be productive and efficient organizational members. Therefore, Enugu State Local Governments needs to minimize if not totally eliminate those factors that are detrimental to organizational performance and goals. These factors include high rate of absenteeism, low productivity, low morale and lack of acceptance and adaptation to organizational changes. This is because if productivity is low and workers are not motivated, then the manager should be blamed. Managers should embrace a more positive way of tapping the inherent potentials of man and the possibilities that abounds. As theory "Y" managers are more likely to create room for trust than theory "X"; trust is an important factor for human resources development. This trust in the organization requires that managers communicate openly with subordinates, minimizing the difference in superior – subordinate relations, creating a comfortable environment that enables subordinates to develop, and use their abilities. This climate of peace above all includes effective participatory democracy which involves sharing in decision making of the enterprise. In view of the stated principles of theory "Y", Enugu State local Government staff requires proper expansion of knowledge and communication through training to maximize their creative, imaginative and problem solving capabilities to improve organizational performance. To this end, the inherent potentials of workers as unveiled by McGregor's theory "Y" will be fully tapped, performance boosted and organizational goals actualized in Enugu State Local Governments through workers participation in decision making.

DATA PRESENTATION FOR THE STUDY

Degree of workers participation in decision making in Enugu State Local Governments, Nigeria

The first hypothesis was aimed at providing certain evidence on the degree of workers participation in decision making in Enugu State local government. In recent time, attempts have

been made by scholars in making explanation of decision-making process and formulation of policies especially at the grass-root level in Enugu State and Nigeria at large. One of the most important dimensions of organizations is decision making. How decisions are made, by what standards, at what cost, and for whose benefit are questions of continuing interest. Decision-making is the process of choosing among alternatives in order to satisfy the objectives or meet the criteria of the decision goal. Decision-making is synonymous with the practice of any government in power. In local government system, decisions are affected by many other factors, including rulings by the courts, societal values, economic conditions, and the values of the people involved in decision-making processes of any administration. Although decisions are often regarded as the product of an individual mind, organizational decision-making is usually a collective process, the end result of the combined efforts of many individuals at many different levels in the hierarchy. During our in-depth interview with one of the staff in Uzo-Uwani Local Government Area who claimed anonymous, He said:

The decision makers in my local government are made by the top management which includes the Head of personnel management, head of other departments such as accounting department, works dept; health etc. That decision come from above. He further stated that there exist two major types of decisions such as the commission decisions, which are reflected in the output or policies that are generated, and internal decisions that affect day-to-day operations within the local government. The Commission's decisions may be thought of in terms of the political dimension.

This view was supported by Jeffrey (2005), that decisions may not affect major policy matters that go beyond the organization. Regardless of the type of decision, models of decision making provide frameworks to illustrate how individuals and groups make decisions in organizations. In a similar dimension an informant who cut in said:

After arriving at a conclusion in any board meeting as the case may be, the various heads of Department, through circular and circular letter communicates to their subordinates or respective departments. If the decision is not meant for external consumption, the heads communicate to themselves through memo. Also, majority of the key informants from the selected local government visited responded positively

that, the style of decision making in their respective local government has negative impact on performance (Interview section, 12th September, 2018).

As stated by one respondent:

As a person, I found it difficult to adapt to changes that was imposed on me. I can perform better when I take part in initiating those changes. Group decision making is being determined by view majority which is no unconnected with issues of politics and the quest for resources appropriation. as the process of a judgment based upon the input of multiple individuals. Since the resources involved in the group decision-making process as well as the impact of these decisions affect organization performance, it is crucial to make the group decision-making process as efficient and effective as possible (Interview section, 15th September, 2018).

Workers' participation in decision making is not significantly linked to organizational performance.

Decision making is a product of bargaining that takes place among many influential participants in governmental-politics. This was supported by Allison, (1999) that decision making focuses on the 'perceptions, motivations, positions, power, and maneuvers of the politicians who differ in ability to shape the outcome. Participation decision-making is shared influence of managers and employees in a firm; it is also used as a motivational program with the function of enhancing both job satisfaction and individual performance.

In the course of our interview, one of the Staff in Nsukka Local Government Stated:

Only the senior officer and employees were identified to be able to influence decision-making. It is an active influence and both have the power to influence because they control the required skills that councilors rely upon for making decisions. Moreover, influences generated from this cluster are technically-based. She further stated that decision making in her local government is full of pretences sometimes, the top management pretend to seek the opinion of workers in the decision even when they must have concluded on what to do (Interview section, 20th September, 2018).

This shows that the level of participation of majority of the employees in the local government as observed is less than it appears on paper. It was noted that meetings at various level do not happen as frequently as they should. Budget meetings are attended by relatively few, and the language and style of these effectively exclude many staff in the local government. Further,

some key officials dominate decision-making at all levels, but increasingly people are willing to speak out and challenge those in authority depending on the outcome of the meeting. The extent of employee participation in decision making remains narrow.

Challenges to Workers participation in decision making: Leadership style, lack of proper training and communication in Enugu state local governments.

Nwali and Okpata (2013) succinctly state that in every state or organization, the major problem that has often posed threat to its existence is the problem of leadership. Leadership is the act of influencing and inspiring subordinates to perform their duties willingly, competently and enthusiastically for the achievement of the group objectives. Leadership is a way of influencing or motivating people to move towards a common goal. Thus, the onerous task of steering the ship of any state or organization cannot be realized if there are no persons with the constitutional empowerment or enablement to carry out the task of governance/administration, (Nwali and Okpata, 2013). Laurie (2010) defines leadership as the relationship through which one person influences behaviour of other people. This means that the process of leadership cannot be separated from the activities of groups. But, the leadership behaviour relationship is not limited to leader behaviour resulting in subordinating or dynamic behaviour, hence, leadership is a dynamic process. Leadership in the words of Nwali and Nkwede (2013) is the ability of influencing the activities of others without any form of coercion or threat towards the realization of the goals of a group, enterprise, organization or nation. They added that the followers must be influenced to work enthusiastically towards the realization of stated goals. Thus, the function of leadership as Nwali and Nkwede continued to preach should always induce or persuade all subordinates or followers to contribute willingly to organizational needs (Agena and Oketa, 2002). A good and effective leader should take responsibility for his actions and that of his followers not minding the situation. This action can make the leader to exert much influence on his followers and the followers having confidence in their leaders. A leader who abandons his followers in the face of responsibility cannot command respect and influence in such an organization or society.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

From the chi-square tests conducted, the research hypotheses I, 2, 3 and 4 were invalidated with regards to workers participation in decision making in Enugu state local governments, Nigeria.

In view of the first hypothesis which postulates a high degree of workers participation in decision making, there was a high level of disagreement as greater number of the workers indicated that they do not participate in the decision making of the organization. Only 34 (12.64%) indicated that they have a say in the decision making. From the focus group discussion and oral interviews conducted, some employees that indicated that they have a say in the decision making, further revealed that the participation is not effective on the premise that conclusions were already made on issues before seeking their opinions or contributions. It then means that their opinion remains irrelevant. This is what the researcher termed pseudo – participation. Pseudo – participation means not genuine. It entails false or pretended. It is a directive management covered with a mask.

The findings of this study also revealed the impacts workers participation in decision making on organizational performance which includes high morale, commitment to organizational goals, and increase in productivity, acceptance and adaptation to change, low turnover rate and low rate of absenteeism. These were ascertained through oral interview, focus group discussions and questionnaire. Therefore, these impacts invalidated the research hypothesis II which postulates that participation in decision making is not significantly linked to organizational performance. Employees further reviewed that participation in decision making has little impacts on workers morale as there are other monetary rewards that impacts more on workers morale. To this regards, a greater percentage of the employees disagreed that participation in decision making amounts to high morale. Through focus group discussions and oral interview, apart from the options in the questionnaire, the workers also identified increase in productivity, and low rate of absenteeism as some of the impacts of workers participation in decision making on organizational performance in Enugu state local governments.

As the study recorded low level workers participation in decision making in Enugu state local governments, the workers revealed the difficulty associated with being committed to the goals that were not initiated by them as well as adapting to changes that are sudden hence, were not initiated or planned by the workers. To this regards, the workers do not see themselves as organizational citizens as they refer to the organization as “they” rather than “we”. This gives

rise to non-challant attitude to work to the detriment of the entire performance and productivity of the organization. This shows that participation in decision making is significantly linked to organizational performance in Enugu state local governments, Nigeria.

The study also exposed the employees to some factors that can hinder effective workers participation in decision making in Enugu state local government. These factors include lack of proper training and communication, leadership style, undue interference and absence of democratically elected leaders.

The findings revealed that lack of interest is not one of the factors that hinder workers participation in decision making. In view of this, greater percentage of the respondents disagreed that lack of interest in participatory decision making hinders effective workers participation in decision making in the local governments. This means that there is interest in participatory decision making in Enugu state local governments but, a lot of factors renders this interest fruitless.

There is a high level of agreement from the respondents that absence of democratically elected leaders hinders effective workers participation in decision making in Enugu state local government. The use of care-taker committee to administer local government council has rendered participatory decision making a myth rather than reality in Enugu state local governments. This undemocratic process denies the workers the most desired participation. Due to the fact that local government chairman elections do not hold, the governor remains the representatives' responsiveness rather than the people. The council chairman are hand-picked by the governors, with the assurance that they cannot be removed or dropped hence, do not, possess the constitutional mandate to question any strange directive in the administration of the local level.

This state of affairs is also linked to undue interference and leadership style which majority of the employees indicated as part of the factors that hinders effective workers participation in decision making in Enugu state local governments. The external intrusion into the affairs of local governments subverts democratic process at the local levels. The existence of local government and its importance has not been justified. Despite the constitutional provisions for local government system consequent upon the 1979 constitution and subsequent ones which defined the function and sources of funding for the council, local governments have not been able to extricate themselves from the apron string of state and federal levels of governments in Nigeria (FRN, 1999). The high level of interference in local affairs undermines

their autonomy. Governor Chime aptly captured the autonomy of local government councils as provided in 1999 constitution, but some governors' greed as revealed by *Lion News Watch*, 2013 vol. 10, did not give freed hand for chairman to operate with their funds independently. This undue interference and leadership style incapacitated effective workers participation in decision making which subverts democratic process/leadership.

The financial paucity in the local government system is an outcome of what should be seen as distributive federalism in a federal state dominated by redistribution of centrally collected revenue. Enugu state local governments seem to have been comfortable with the monthly allocation from the federation account which has remained a distributive outlet for federal and state generated revenue. For instance, former president Obasanjo, in a meeting with 774 local government council chairmen once acknowledge diversion of local government fund by some state governors. He argued that the proposed technical committee will look into the matter through local and state joint account; some states arbitrarily deduct from local government account and forced them to embark on projects that are not in congruence with the needs of the people under the pretext of uniform development according to *Radio Nigeria*, 2004.

This lack of fund in Enugu state Local Government has implication on expansion of knowledge and communication through training. The findings of this study further revealed a high level of agreement from the respondents as to whether lack of proper training and communication hinders workers participation in decision making. The employees' lacks the requisite training and knowledge that enables good decision as revealed through the focus group discussions hence, once cannot offer what he do not have. From these findings, it was established that the research hypothesis III which stated that effective workers participation in decision making is not hindered by leadership style and lack of proper training is invalidated as effective workers participation in decision making is hindered by leadership style, lack of proper training and communication in Enugu state local governments, Nigeria.

The findings of this study further revealed that the fourth research hypothesis is not true as effective workers participation in decision making can be enhanced through effective participation democracy and proper training. The findings also recorded a high-level agreement from the respondents as to whether elimination of undue interference and proper funding of the local governments can enhance workers participation in decision making in Enugu state local governments, Nigeria. The study also revealed a high level of disagreement in view of Job

enrichment, expansion of knowledge and communication through training as one of the strategies to enhance participation in decision making. The focus group discussion further revealed that expansion of knowledge and communication through training as well as job enrichment without democratizing the decision-making process, effective participation remains a myth in Enugu state local governments. It then means that participatory democracy and proper training are some of the strategies through which effective workers participation in decision making can be enhanced in Enugu state local governments, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Workers participation in decision making has significant impact on organizational performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that the essence of workers participation in decision making cannot be underestimated because it motivates workers to be committed to the organizational goals. The implication of this for public sector organizations is the need to acknowledge the essence of involving workers in decision making. Also, if workers are allowed to actively participate in decision making, it would reduce turnover, absenteeism and increase productivity. Not only does workers participation in decision creates room for the previous points, it also gives management the chance of having a better understanding of the mindset of the workers that are put in place, policies that can address the needs of the workers. In view of these, Enugu State Local Governments should desist from pseudo participations which is prevalence in the local governments and embrace practical and effective participatory decision making to make ends meet.

REFERENCES

- Agena, J.E., and Oketa, C. N. (2002). *The State and Citizen: A fundamental approach*. Enugu: Jones communication publishers.
- Allison, G.T., & Zelikow, P. (1999). *Essence of Decision: Explaining the Cuban Missile Crisis*, 2nd edn. New York: Longman.
- Bell, C., & Mjoli, T. (2014). The effects of participative leadership on organizational commitment: comparing its effects on two gender groups among bank clerks. *African Journal of Business Management*, 8(12): 451-459.
- Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria (2004). “*State of the Nation*” A network service programme broadcast on January 5th by 7pm.

- Helms, Van Der (2007). *With participation comes dilemmas*. Retrieved on 4 March 2011 from <http://www.academiejourals.org/ERR/PDF/pdf1%20209/August/Mualuko%20et%20al.pdf>.
- Iranwanto, D.W. (2015). Employee participation in Decision Making: Evidence from State owned Enterprise. *Management*, 20(1), 159-172.
- Kartz, D. & Khan, R.L. (1979). *The social psychology of organization*. New York: John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Laurie, J. M. (2010). *Management & Organisational Behaviour*. Ninth Edition, (Great Britain: Prentice Hall, p.373.
- Lerner, A. (2011). 'McGregor's legacy: thoughts on what he left, what transpired, and what remains to pursue', *Journal of Management History*, 17 (2), pp. 217-237 JSTOR [Online]. Available at: <http://emeraldinsight.com/1751-1348.htm> (Accessed: 1 July 2013).
- Lundgrem, E.E. (1982). *Organizational management system and processes*. San Francisco: Canfield Press.
- MacGregor, D. (1960). *The Human side of enterprise*. New York; McGraw Hill.
- Miller, K. I., & Monge, P. R. (1986). The development and test of a system of organizational participation and allocation. In M. McLaughlin (Ed.), *Communication yearbook 10*: inpress. Beverly Hills, Calif.: Sage Publications
- Nwali, T. B., & Okpata, F. O. (2013). *Public Sector Administration in Nigeria*. Abakaliki: De Oasis Communications and publishers.
- Nwali, T. B., & Nkwede, J. O. (2011). Public Private Partnership in the Development of Public Sector Administration in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Review* vol. 2 (3)
- Nwizu, G. (2002). *Studies in modern public administration*. Enugu: NGTB Publishers Ltd.
- Spreitzer, G. M., Kizilos, M., & Nason, S. (1997). "A dimensional analysis of empowerment in relation to performance, job satisfaction, and job-related strain." *Journal of Management*, 23 (5), 679-704.
- Summers, J. & Hyman, J. (2005). *Employee participation and Company Performance*, A review of the literature, Joseph Rowntree Foundation. www.jrf.org.uk (ISBN 1 85935 299 5)